

NEW APPROACHES TO MAKE A CLASSROOM MORE INNOVATIVE

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Abstract. *In this article, I will focus on some of the most creative and innovative areas which make the classrooms convenient learning zone. To create an innovative, open, creative and trustworthy place for students to grow, take risks, and feel comfortable in their own patterns of learning, there are a few key actions teachers can take to create a more innovative and entrepreneurial classroom.*

Key words: *approach, classroom, innovation, creativeness, learning, teaching, motivation, inspiration.*

НОВЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ, КОТОРЫЕ СДЕЛАЮТ КЛАСС БОЛЕЕ ИННОВАЦИОННЫМ

Аннотация. *В этой статье я сосредоточусь на некоторых из самых творческих и инновационных областей, которые делают классы удобной зоной обучения. Чтобы создать инновационное, открытое, творческое и заслуживающее доверия место, где учащиеся могли бы расти, рисковать и чувствовать себя комфортно в своих собственных моделях обучения, учителя могут предпринять несколько ключевых действий, чтобы создать более инновационный и предприимчивый класс.*

Ключевые слова: *подход, класс, инновации, творчество, обучение, обучение, мотивация, вдохновение.*

INTRODUCTION

I view culture as one of the most critical aspects to invite innovation and make the classroom a safe place to create, ask questions, and fail in order to learn. Teachers create the mood and tone of the room. Positive classroom cultures that invite authentic learning can lead to more opportunities for students to positively connect with content, their peers, and their teacher.

METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

Here are nine ways teachers can create innovative learning spaces:

1. Mindset. A change in mindset, mood, and overall classroom vibe begins with the teacher. The teacher sets the tone of the class from the minute students walk into the building. If educators are excited about their subject matter, students will tend to follow. Educators must have passion for the subjects they're teaching. However, a teacher's mindset regarding how to design and deliver content is critical to the innovative learning process. Most teachers were trained to educate solely from the teacher's point of view.

2. Self-Reflection. Self-reflection in the classroom is a way for educators to look back on their teaching strategies to discover how and why they were teaching in a certain way and how their students responded.

With a profession as challenging as teaching, self-reflection can offer teachers a critical opportunity to see what worked and what failed in their classroom. Educators can use reflective teaching as a way to analyze and evaluate their own teaching practices so they can focus on what

works. Effective teachers acknowledge the fact that teaching strategies, delivery and finding success can always be improved.

3. Ask Open-Ended Questions. Open-ended questions are questions without textbook answers. When educators ask open-ended questions, there can be various answers and points of view. Student answers can lead to strong collaboration, exciting conversations, new ideas, as well as encourage leadership skills. This practice can also help students realize potential they never found within themselves. Through open-ended questions, they can also make connections to their own lives, within other stories, or to real-world events.

4. Create Flexible Learning Environments. With various teaching methods, it's essential for teachers to consider how to use their classroom space. For example, when teachers can move furniture around the class with ease, they can find it is a crucial variable for improving student learning. As teaching has evolved, the classroom space must provide ways for students to work alone, interact with their peers, and provide areas of collaboration. Many classrooms today are still crowded, cluttered, loud spaces that lack the space to move around with ease, cause a gap in communication, and lead to roadblocks when students need to concentrate.

Learning spaces should be fluid and provide flexibility to support one-to-one learning, collaboration, independent thinking, and group discussions.

5. Personality Matters: Create A Place For All Learners. In Susan Cain's book, *Quiet: The Power of Introverts in a World That Can't Stop Talking*, one of the critical differences between introverts and extroverts is that extroverts tend to get their energy from social interaction and introverts gain energy from quiet spaces and a time to think and reflect alone. Therefore, when a classroom solely focuses on group work-which emphasizes whole group discussions, small groups working together, gathering peer feedback (all which require a great deal of social interaction), extroverts in the classroom can grow and gain energy, while introverted students can find themselves easily drained with a lack of motivation to participate.

6. Use Problem-Finding. Instead of problem-solving, teachers can help students look at the world by finding gaps to fill using problem-finding. Problem-finding is equivalent to problem discovery. Teachers can use problem-finding as part of a more significant problem process as a whole that can include problem-shaping and problem-solving all together. Problem-finding requires an intellectual and imaginative vision to seek out what might be missing or should be added to something important. Using this strategy, teachers can provide students with the opportunity to think deeply, ask critical questions and apply creative ways to solve problems.

7. Let Students Take Risks and Fail. Students need to see that adults in their lives try many things and repeatedly fail, but keep on trying. Students need to experience failure to learn.

8. Consider A Flipped Classroom Model. When teachers use a flipped classroom model, the traditional order of teaching and classroom events are reversed. Typically, students can view lecture materials, read text, or do research as their homework prior to coming into class. The time spent in class is reserved for activities that can include peer-to-peer learning, group discussions, independent learning, as well as engaging discussions or collaborative work.

9. Use The Design-Thinking Process. The [design thinking process](#) is a set of structured strategies that identify challenges, gather information, generate potential solutions, refine ideas, and test solutions. There are five phases to the process: discovery, interpretation, ideation, experimentation, and evolution.

CONCLUSION

To conclude, all of these strategies are ways to form innovation and inspire creativity in the classroom. Teachers can start with one new project to see how things go with their students while revising, learning and building repeatedly. Innovation is a necessary change we need in schools today, and it can begin with you.

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